

OS-VAL
C13-NMR

The University of Jordan
Faculty of Science
Department of Chemistry

Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
Operator: Rola Hassouneh
nmr500@ju.edu.jo

Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1912
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 11.23 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 ()
PULPROG zgpg30
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 173
DS 4
SMH 31250.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.953674 Hz
AQ 1.0485760 sec
RG 202.06
DW 16.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.1 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
D11 0.03000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 125.7700308 MHz
NUC1 13C
P0 3.33 usec
P1 10.00 usec
PLW1 92.99600220 W
SFO2 500.1320005 MHz
NUC2 1H
CPDPRG[2] waltz16
PCPD2 80.00 usec
PLW2 14.30399990 W
PLW12 0.32183000 W
PLW13 0.16188000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 32768
SF 125.7577890 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 1.00 Hz
GB 0
PC 1.50

OS-VAL
X
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Instrument Model:
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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1922
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters

Date_ 20230924
Time 11.51 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD Z119470_0023 ()
PULPROG zgpg30
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 457
DS 4
SWH 31250.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.953674 Hz
AQ 1.0485760 sec
RG 202.06
DW 16.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
D11 0.03000000 sec
TD0 1
SF01 125.7700308 MHz
NUC1 13C
P0 3.33 usec
P1 10.00 usec
PLW1 92.99600220 W
SFO2 500.1320005 MHz
NUC2 1H
CPDPRG[2] waltz16
FCPD2 80.00 usec
PLW2 14.30399990 W
PLW12 0.32183000 W
PLW13 0.16188000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 32768
SF 125.7577890 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 1.00 Hz
GB 0
PC 2.00

OS-PH
C13-NMR

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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1942
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 12.42 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 {
PULPROG zgpg30
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 202
DS 4
SWH 31250.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.953674 Hz
AQ 1.0485760 sec
RG 202.06
DW 16.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
D11 0.03000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 125.7700308 MHz
NUC1 13C
P0 3.33 usec
F1 10.00 usec
PLW1 92.99600220 W
SFO2 500.1320005 MHz
NUC2 1H
CPDPRG[2] waltz16
PCPD2 80.00 usec
PLW2 14.30399990 W
PLW12 0.32183000 W
PLW13 0.16188000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 32768
SF 125.7577890 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 1.00 Hz
GB 0
PC 2.00

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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1952
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters

Date_ 20230924
Time 13.17 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 f
PULPROG zgpg30
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 315
DS 4
SMH 31250.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.953674 Hz
AQ 1.0485760 sec
RG 202.06
DW 16.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.1 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
D11 0.03000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 125.7700308 MHz
NUC1 13C
P0 3.33 usec
P1 10.00 usec
PLW1 92.99600220 W
SFO2 500.1320005 MHz
NUC2 1H
CPDPRG[2] waltz16
PCPD2 80.00 usec
PLW2 14.30399990 W
PLW12 0.32183000 W
PLW13 0.16188000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 32768
SF 125.7577890 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 1.00 Hz
GB 0
PC 2.00

Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
Operator: Rola Hassounh
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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1872
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters

Date_ 20230924
Time 10.35 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD Z119470_0023 (
PULPROG zgpg30
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 2052
DS 4
SWH 31250.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.953674 Hz
AQ 1.0485760 sec
RG 202.06
DW 16.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
D11 0.03000000 sec
TD0 1
SF01 125.7700308 MHz
NUC1 13C
P0 3.33 usec
P1 10.00 usec
PLW1 92.99600220 W
SFO2 500.1320005 MHz
NUC2 1H
CPDPRG2 waltz16
PCPD2 80.00 usec
PLW2 14.30399990 W
PLW12 0.32183000 W
PLW13 0.16188000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 32768
SF 125.7577890 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 1.00 Hz
GB 0
PC 2.00

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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1902
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 14.17 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD Z119470_0023 f
PULPROG zgpg30
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 1135
DS 4
SWH 31250.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.953674 Hz
AQ 1.0485760 sec
RG 202.06
DW 16.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
D11 0.03000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 125.7700308 MHz
NUC1 13C
P0 3.33 usec
P1 10.00 usec
PLW1 92.99600220 W
SFO2 500.1320005 MHz
NUC2 1H
PCPDPRG2 waltz16
PCPD2 80.00 usec
PLW2 14.30399990 W
PLW12 0.32183000 W
PLW13 0.16188000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 32768
SF 125.7577890 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 1.00 Hz
GB 0
FC 2.00

Instrument Model:
Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III
Operator: Rola Hassouneh
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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1892
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 11.00 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 (
PULPROG zgpg30
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 250
DS 4
SWH 31250.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.953674 Hz
AQ 1.0485760 sec
RG 202.06
DW 16.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.0 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
D11 0.03000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 125.7700308 MHz
NUC1 13C
P0 3.33 usec
P1 10.00 usec
PLW1 92.99600220 W
SFO2 500.1320005 MHz
NUC2 1H
CPDPRG[2] waltz16
PCPD2 80.00 usec
PLM2 14.30399990 W
PLW2 0.32183000 W
PLM13 0.16188000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 32768
SF 125.7577890 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 1.00 Hz
GB 0
PC 2.00

171.1729
167.3332
165.5743

138.9111
138.2167
130.8991
128.2292
127.4385
115.7696

81.6140
81.5734
74.5585
74.3926
61.1312
52.6612
49.3557
49.1977
40.4999
40.4098
40.3307
40.2424
40.1644
40.0754
39.9975
39.9083
39.7414
39.5742
39.4076
28.6212
26.0776
25.5211
23.7912
14.5310
9.8380
9.3025

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Current Data Parameters
NAME 23sep15jalal
EXPNO 1932
PROCNO 1

F2 - Acquisition Parameters
Date_ 20230924
Time 12.26 h
INSTRUM spect
PROBHD z119470_0023 ()
PULPROG zgpg30
TD 65536
SOLVENT DMSO
NS 595
DS 4
SWH 31250.000 Hz
FIDRES 0.953674 Hz
AQ 1.0485760 sec
RG 202.06
DW 16.000 usec
DE 6.50 usec
TE 298.1 K
D1 2.00000000 sec
D11 0.03000000 sec
TD0 1
SFO1 125.7700308 MHz
NUC1 13C
P0 3.33 usec
P1 10.00 usec
PLM1 92.99600220 W
SFO2 500.1320005 MHz
NUC2 1H
CPDPRG[2] waltz16
PCPD2 80.00 usec
PLM2 14.30399990 W
PLM12 0.32183000 W
PLM13 0.16188000 W

F2 - Processing parameters
SI 32768
SF 125.7577890 MHz
WDW EM
SSB 0
LB 1.00 Hz
GB 0
PC 2.00